

STEPS OF FORMATION OF DIFFERENTIATED TEACHING IN PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

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Abstract. The article considers the characteristic features of the retrospective development of differentiated education in our country, analyzes theoretical sources containing historical and pedagogical research on this problem, describes the stages of formation of profile differentiation in the direction of pedagogical training in order to increase the efficiency and optimize the learning process of future specialists. Based on the periodizations of differentiated learning existing in pedagogical science and the analysis of theoretical sources, a periodization of the development of differentiated learning in pedagogy is proposed, reflecting a historical and logical view of this pedagogical phenomenon. Currently, the changes taking place in the education system affect such significant problems as the emergence of new technical equipment and information support, the need to take into account the features of multi-level education in universities (bachelor's- master's-doctoral studies). These changes have an impact on the system of differentiated training of future specialists in universities. The problem of differentiated education of students in higher education institutions requires further historical and pedagogical understanding, search for directions for effective development, modernization and development of new approaches to training and professional development of future specialists.

Keywords: differentiated training; profile orientation; individualization; department; training center at the university; training of future specialists, the system of training specialists.

Introduction. Changes in the socio-economic and political life of modern society, the humanistic concept and the “restructuring of the higher education system at all levels” determine the search for further ways to develop differentiated education. The analysis of the accumulated historical and pedagogical experience is necessary to increase the effectiveness of the development of individual educational trajectories and create pedagogical conditions for the comprehensive development of the personality of students of higher educational institutions. The insufficient number of historical and

pedagogical studies on the problem of differentiated education, taking into account the profile specifics of training future specialists in universities and the lack of generalization of experience on this issue prevents the successful implementation of differentiated education in departments and training centers of universities, does not allow taking into account the individual characteristics of students in full [9, p. 192].

The scientific understanding of the development of differentiated learning in the modern domestic educational space, the analysis of the acquired experience and traditions is relevant in order to determine new prospects for the development of specialized education, the development of innovative concepts for the organization of differentiated learning, taking into account interdisciplinary and competence-based approaches to higher education.

The study of the historical and pedagogical stages of the formation of differentiated education in order to improve the level of training of future specialists in universities will allow the followings:

- systematize the conceptual apparatus on this problem;
- to carry out a more in-depth analysis of various approaches to differentiated learning;
- to avoid the formation of identical profile areas and unjustified fragmentation of specialties;
- improve the quality of training
- take into account the shortcomings and identify the prospects for profile and level differentiation of training;
- effectively use the profile specialization of technical university students to search for innovative learning paths in departments and training centers.

Object of the research and methods. The majority of scientific works on the problems of the formation of differentiated education are devoted to the study of this process at school, “school business” [6, p. 180], “is mainly connected with the educational process of secondary schools” [2, p. 206]. The space of higher educational institutions is still not fully explored; the historical periods of the development of the pedagogical theory of specialized education are insufficiently represented, taking into account the specifics of training future specialists in universities. In this regard, the features and trends in the development of differentiated teaching of pedagogical students in universities have not been fully identified and require further research.

In the works of researchers, the concept of “differentiated learning” does not have an unambiguous definition due to the lack of a single terminological apparatus on this issue. In English, the term “differentiation” (“difference”)

means difference, separation, differentiation, distinguishing feature, isolation, modification.

K.G. Selevko defines differentiated learning as a form of organization of the educational process, when a teacher works with a homogeneous group of students who have common qualities that are significant for the educational process and as part of a common didactic system in the space of which the specialization of teaching of various groups of students is realized [12, p. 229].

A.A. Kirsanov understands differentiated learning as “a system of educational and didactic means that correspond to the goals of activity and the real cognitive capabilities of the class collective, individual students and groups of students, allowing for the student’s educational activity at the level of his potential, taking into account the learning goals” [7, p. 138].

Analyzing the features of the development of differentiated learning, researcher V.I. Pisarenko rightly notes that “a personality-oriented approach is considered as an alternative to the traditional socio-oriented one” [9, p. 99], and the implementation of learning goals should be carried out within the framework of a personality-oriented paradigm based on communicative, competence-based, professionally-oriented and stylistic approaches [9, p. 101].

V.A. Romanov, considering the integration of special disciplines of the department and general disciplines of a university, notes the importance of implementing in practice the selection of “the content of special training of students taking into account their individual characteristics and needs” [11, p. 256].

The issues affecting the problems of differentiated learning, individual approach, personality-oriented paradigm of the learning process at the university are reflected in the works of Y.K. Babansky, I.A. Zimnaya, V.V. Kraevsky, N.V. Kuzmina, V.V. Serikov and other researchers.

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